

DEX2TKA simulations

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Simulated data

```
#Number of participants
n_part <- 485
df <- NULL

#Random assignment to the three groups
df$group <- as.factor(sample(c(1:3),n_part, replace=TRUE))

#Random assignment to the sites
df$site <- sample(c("A","B","C"),n_part, replace=TRUE)

#Random assignment to age
df$bc_age <- rnorm(n_part, mean=65, sd=8)
df$bc_ASA_above_2 <- sample(c(0,1),n_part, replace=TRUE)
df$bc_High_pain_at_rest <- rnorm(n_part, mean=30, sd=10)
df$bc_High_pain_when_active <- rnorm(n_part, mean=30, sd=10)
df$bc_Only_spinal <- sample(c(0,1),n_part, replace=TRUE)
df$bc_Prior_pain_med <- sample(c(0,1),n_part, replace=TRUE)
df$bc_BMI <- rnorm(n_part, mean=30, sd=4)

df <- data.frame(df)
df$age <- 0
df$age[df$bc_age > 65] <- 1

df_mc <- df

#The simulated outcome depending on the median for each group:
n_dd <- 35
n_dp <- 38
n_pp <- 43
df$outcome[df$group==1] <- rnorm(sum((df$group==1)*1),mean=n_dd,sd=5)
df$outcome[df$group==2] <- rnorm(sum((df$group==2)*1),mean=n_dp,sd=5)
df$outcome[df$group==3] <- rnorm(sum((df$group==3)*1),mean=n_pp,sd=5)

#The simulated RRR of age:
rrr_age <- 0.1
df$outcome[df$age == 1] <- df$outcome[df$age == 1]-df$outcome[df$age == 1]*rrr_age
```

Baseline characteristics for subgroup

```
library(tableone)
CreateTableOne(c("bc_age", "bc_BMI", "bc_ASA_above_2", "bc_High_pain_at_rest", "bc_High_pain_when_active",
  "bc_Only_spinal", "bc_Prior_pain_med"), strata = c("age", "group"),
  factorVars = c("bc_ASA_above_2", "bc_Only_spinal", "bc_Prior_pain_med"),
  data=df, test=FALSE)
```

```
##                               Stratified by age:group
##                               0:1           1:1
##  n                               81           76
##  bc_age (mean (SD))              58.40 (4.65) 71.01 (4.90)
##  bc_BMI (mean (SD))              30.00 (3.79) 29.30 (3.79)
##  bc_ASA_above_2 = 1 (%)           41 (50.6)  45 (59.2)
##  bc_High_pain_at_rest (mean (SD)) 29.28 (9.40) 30.50 (9.56)
##  bc_High_pain_when_active (mean (SD)) 31.05 (10.00) 29.55 (8.84)
##  bc_Only_spinal = 1 (%)           38 (46.9)  36 (47.4)
##  bc_Prior_pain_med = 1 (%)        39 (48.1)  34 (44.7)
##                               Stratified by age:group
##                               0:2           1:2
##  n                               71           78
##  bc_age (mean (SD))              59.49 (4.42) 70.93 (4.92)
##  bc_BMI (mean (SD))              29.95 (4.24) 29.99 (4.23)
##  bc_ASA_above_2 = 1 (%)           27 (38.0)  38 (48.7)
##  bc_High_pain_at_rest (mean (SD)) 32.68 (12.43) 31.61 (10.56)
##  bc_High_pain_when_active (mean (SD)) 29.73 (9.50) 30.52 (10.82)
##  bc_Only_spinal = 1 (%)           36 (50.7)  35 (44.9)
##  bc_Prior_pain_med = 1 (%)        28 (39.4)  37 (47.4)
##                               Stratified by age:group
##                               0:3           1:3
##  n                               86           93
##  bc_age (mean (SD))              58.59 (4.81) 71.68 (4.97)
##  bc_BMI (mean (SD))              29.53 (3.67) 30.12 (3.97)
##  bc_ASA_above_2 = 1 (%)           41 (47.7)  42 (45.2)
##  bc_High_pain_at_rest (mean (SD)) 31.73 (9.62) 30.29 (9.94)
##  bc_High_pain_when_active (mean (SD)) 30.49 (11.03) 29.38 (9.56)
##  bc_Only_spinal = 1 (%)           41 (47.7)  42 (45.2)
##  bc_Prior_pain_med = 1 (%)        43 (50.0)  47 (50.5)
```

Quantile regression for interaction only

```
#https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/quantreg/vignettes/rq.pdf  
#install.packages("quantreg")  
suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(library(quantreg)))  
fit_rq <- rq(outcome ~ group*age,data=df)
```

```
## Warning in rq.fit.br(x, y, tau = tau, ...): Solution may be nonunique
```

```
summary(fit_rq,se="nid")
```

```
##  
## Call: rq(formula = outcome ~ group * age, data = df)  
##  
## tau: [1] 0.5  
##  
## Coefficients:  
##           Value      Std. Error t value Pr(>|t|)  
## (Intercept) 34.64455  0.62947  55.03749  0.00000  
## group2      3.65202  1.23630   2.95398  0.00329  
## group3      8.70705  1.00415   8.67107  0.00000  
## age        -3.10804  0.82288  -3.77702  0.00018  
## group2:age -0.47171  1.46960  -0.32098  0.74837  
## group3:age -1.31063  1.23464  -1.06155  0.28897
```

```
#https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/aod/versions/1.3.1/topics/wald.test  
#install.packages("aod")  
suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(library(aod)))  
#https://www.rdocumentation.org/packages/Zelig/versions/5.1.7/topics/vcov_rq  
#install.packages("Zelig")  
suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(library(Zelig)))  
wald.test(b = coef(fit_rq), Sigma = vcov_rq(fit_rq), Terms = 5:6)
```

```
## Wald test:  
## -----  
##  
## Chi-squared test:  
## X2 = 1.1, df = 2, P(> X2) = 0.57
```

Van Elteren p-values

```
#https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/sanon/sanon.pdf
#install.packages("sanon")
suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(library(sanon)))

df_test <- df[df$age == 0 & (df$group == "1" | df$group == "2"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="1") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "1") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##      Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome   0.1707  0.0455  14.1   0.00017 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

```
df_test <- df[df$age == 0 & (df$group == "1" | df$group == "3"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="1") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "1") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##      Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome   0.3992  0.0242   273    <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

```
df_test <- df[df$age == 0 & (df$group == "2" | df$group == "3"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="2") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "2") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##      Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome   0.2663  0.0377   49.8   1.7e-12 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

```
df_test <- df[df$age == 1 & (df$group == "1" | df$group == "2"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="1") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "1") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##           Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome    0.1978  0.0443  19.9    8.1e-06 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

```
df_test <- df[df$age == 1 & (df$group == "1" | df$group == "3"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="1") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "1") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##           Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome    0.4040  0.0234   297    <2e-16 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

```
df_test <- df[df$age == 1 & (df$group == "2" | df$group == "3"),]
summary(sanon(outcome ~ grp(group, ref="2") + str(site), data=df_test))
```

```
## Call:
## sanon.formula(formula = outcome ~ grp(group, ref = "2") + str(site),
##   data = df_test)
##
##
##           Estimate Std.Err Chisq Pr(>Chisq)
## outcome    0.2445  0.0392    39    4.2e-10 ***
## ---
## Signif. codes:  0 '***' 0.001 '**' 0.01 '*' 0.05 '.' 0.1 ' ' 1
## Note that the estimates of responses are for the (MW estimate - 0.5).
```

Hodges-Lemann median differences

```
#https://rdrr.io/cran/DescTools/man/HodgesLehmann.html  
#install.packages("DescTools")  
suppressMessages(suppressWarnings(library("DescTools")))
```

```
#Sammenligning mellem aldersgrupper i hver gruppe  
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 1 & df$age == 0],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 2 & df$age == 0],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -3.0577938 -5.1431926 -0.9508709
```

```
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 1 & df$age == 0],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 3 & df$age == 0],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -8.405907 -10.300894 -6.602105
```

```
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 2 & df$age == 0],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 3 & df$age == 0],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -5.402509 -7.479059 -3.298164
```

```
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 1 & df$age == 1],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 2 & df$age == 1],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -3.204365 -4.797497 -1.397309
```

```
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 1 & df$age == 1],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 3 & df$age == 1],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -7.287141 -8.749119 -5.665037
```

```
HodgesLehmann(df$outcome[df$group == 2 & df$age == 1],  
              df$outcome[df$group == 3 & df$age == 1],  
              conf.level = 0.983)
```

```
##      est      lwr.ci      upr.ci  
## -4.068798 -5.736961 -2.477672
```